

VERIFICATION OF PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH CONSTRUCTION

Masakazu Sano *, Tadashi Koga*, Tomohiro Yokozeki**, Toshio Ogasawara**
[Masakazu Sano/ Tadashi Koga]:sano@ivis.co.jp
koga@ivis.co.jp

*IVIS INC., HONGO OGI BLDG., 3-6-6 Hongo, Bunkyo-Ku, Tokyo 113-0033, Japan
Tel:+81 3 5800 0780, Fax:+81 3 5800 0781, Email:sano@ivis.co.jp

** Advanced Composite Technology Center, Institute of Aerospace Technology(IAT),
Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA), 6-13-1 Osawa, Mitaka, Tokyo 181-0015, Japan
Tel:+81(422)40-3384, Fax:+81(422)40-3549, Email:yokozeki@chofu.jaxa.jp

Keywords: *Progressive failure analysis, Sandwich structure, Calibration, Carbon fiber, Ply-property*

1. Introduction

The sandwich construction composites and the carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) composites have been extensively used in structural components. In order to accurately analyze these materials by finite element method, solid elements have been widely utilized. Although the use of solid elements contributes to improvement in accuracy of analytical results, the task for preparing solid elements is enormous. Therefore, many researchers and engineers have investigated how to improve the accuracy of analysis results based on shell elements. Moreover, in order to improve analytical accuracy, it is necessary to represent the material properties accurately (e.g. stiffness, nonlinearity, strength). For example, longitudinal compressive properties of unidirectional composites vary depending on the test method used. It was reported that compressive strength of 0° CFRP obtained by the four-point flexural test using thin honeycomb sandwich construction composite beam (SDW_Thin) was significantly higher than that by the standard compressive test using coupon specimens [1]. For the effective and accurate simulations of the behaviors of composites and sandwich structures including damage onset and failure, development and verification of progressive failure analyses using shell elements and appropriate material properties should be necessary.

This study investigates the applicability of a GENOA software, which is dedicated for progressive failure analysis, to the failure analysis of composite laminates and sandwich constructions using shell elements. We report the analysis result using two kinds of the compressive properties. One is the value obtained from a standard testing method

of compressive properties of 0° CFRP laminates, and the other is that obtained from the testing method of SDW_Thin. Careful attention has been paid to effects of the selected material properties on the progressive failure analytical results of CFRP laminates and sandwich composite specimens by comparing the predictions with experimental results.

2. The material properties used for analysis

All simulations were analyzed by the analysis software (GENOA), whose copyright was acquired by Alpha STAR Corporation (ASC) from National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). GENOA can handle microscopic properties (fiber and matrix, respectively) for the macroscopic analysis of composite laminates and structures. The selected material system is T800H/3633, carbon fiber epoxy system. Toray Co. Ltd. has published the material properties of the fiber (T800H) as shown in Table 2.1. In order to obtain the other properties of fiber and matrix for analysis, we compared the results of simulation and experiments of unidirectional CFRP, and determined the material properties. We call this work a “calibration”.

Table 2.1 Property values of a T800H⁺

Category	Name	Item	Value	Unit
Fiber	T800HB	normal modulus(11)	2.940E+05	MPa
		tensile strength(11)	5.490E+03	MPa

Experimental stress-strain relations were used for the calibration of the material properties; 1. standard test for tensile properties of polymer matrix composite materials by tensile test of 0 degree and

90 degree laminate. 2. standard test for compressive properties of polymer matrix composite materials by compressive test of 0 degree and 90 degree laminate. 3. standard test for in plane shear response of polymer matrix composite materials by tensile and compressive test of 45 degree laminate. In order to investigate effects of the selected material properties on the progressive failure analytical results, 0° compressive properties obtained by SDW_Thin test method [1] were also used for calibration. The calibrated material properties are shown in Table 2.2, in which there are two kinds of properties. One is the material property (coupon) that was calibrated using the 0° coupon compressive experiment and the other is the material property (SDW_Thin) that was calibrated using the SDW_Thin testing method experiment. The calibrated stress-strain (S-S) curve of EPOXY3633 is shown in Table 2.3. Note that both of stress and strain in this table correspond to an equivalent stress and strain (Mises type).

Table 2.2 The Fiber/Matrix property value for analysis

Category	Name	Item	Coupon	SDW Thin	Unit
Fiber	T800HB				
		normal modulus(11)	2.585E+05	2.585E+05	MPa
		normal modulus(22)	1.800E+04	1.800E+04	MPa
		shear modulus(12)	1.400E+05	1.400E+05	MPa
		shear modulus(23)	1.400E+05	1.400E+05	MPa
		poisson's ratio(12)	0.20	0.20	
		poisson's ratio(23)	0.20	0.20	
		tensile strength(11)	3.900E+03	3.900E+03	MPa
		compressive strength(11)	2.400E+03	3.280E+03	MPa
		tensile strength(22)	1.000E+02	1.000E+02	MPa
		compressive strength(22)	1.000E+02	1.000E+02	MPa
		torsional strength(12)	1.000E+02	1.000E+02	MPa
		torsional strength(23)	1.000E+02	1.000E+02	MPa
Matrix	3633				
		normal modulus	3.500E+03	3.500E+03	MPa
		poisson's ratio	0.35	0.35	
		tensile strength	9.850E+01	9.850E+01	MPa
		compressive strength	2.900E+02	2.900E+02	MPa
		shear strength	9.800E+01	9.800E+01	MPa
		tensile strain	0.015	0.017	
		compressive strain	0.032	0.034	
		shear strain	0.032	0.034	
		torsional strain	0.040	0.040	

Table 2.3 The S-S curve accord with the Mises rule for analysis

EPOXY 3633 S-S	
Strain	Stress
0.000E+00	0.000E+00
1.000E-02	3.500E+01
2.000E-02	7.000E+01
3.000E-02	1.050E+02
4.000E-02	1.290E+02
5.000E-02	1.480E+02
6.000E-02	1.620E+02
7.000E-02	1.740E+02

Fig.2.1 Tensile test of 0 degree laminate

Fig.2.2 Compressive test of 0 degree laminate

Comparison of stress-strain curves between experiments and simulations using the calibrated data are shown in Fig.2.1 - Fig.2.5. The load-displacement relationship of the simulation and experiment of the SDW_thin is shown in Fig. 2.6.

Fig.2.3 Tensile test of 45 degree laminate

Fig.2.4 Tensile test of 90 degree laminate

Fig.2.5 Compressive test of 90 degree laminate

Fig.2.6 Load-Displacement of thin sandwich 4 points flexural testing

3 Compressive analytical result of quasi-isotropic laminate

Using the calibrated coupon properties and the SDW_Thin properties, S-S curves of quasi-isotropic [45/0/-45/90]_{2S} laminate under compressive load are predicted and compared with that of experiment as shown in Fig. 3.1.

Fig.3.1 Compressive S-S curve of quasi-isotropic laminate.

It is shown that the compressive strength of analytical result using the coupon properties exhibits low strength compared to the experimental result. On the other hand, the strength of analytical result using the SDW_Thin properties agrees well with the experimental result. When deciding the material properties by calibration work, it is noted first that the properties based on the compressive experimental result of 0 degree coupon laminate

give the lower compressive strength prediction of quasi-isotropic laminates than those based on the SDW_Thin. The reason of this difference is due to the difficulty in measurement of accurate longitudinal compressive strength using 0° coupon specimens. When using thin coupon specimen, it is difficult to apply pure compressive situation without buckling. If thicker coupon specimens are used, then it is again difficult to measure compressive strength since other damage modes (e.g. splitting) may take place. On the contrary, it is easy to measure compressive strength of unidirectional laminates by the SDW_Thin unless peel off of a face sheet or collapse of the core occur, which are easy to be controlled. Therefore, it is reliable to use the compressive strength obtained by the SDW_thin experimental result for the calibration in order to predict failure behaviors of composite laminates.

4. Four-point flexural analytical results of thin and thick sandwich construction composite beam

GENOA can analyze two types of material model. One is termed as “micro model” which consists of fibers and matrix, and the other is termed as “macro model” which handles fibers and matrix as a homogeneous lamina (Ply Property). The properties of the aluminum honeycomb 1/8-5052-002 presented by Showa Aircraft Industry Co. Ltd. that were used in the experiments conducted by JAXA are shown in Table 4.1. These core properties are incorporated into the software as the macro model in this section. Because GENOA has a function that computes the macro properties from properties of a micro model, macroscopic properties of unidirectional CFRP are calculated using the previous calibrated data. Now we will analyze four-point flexural test of thick and thin beams using shell elements and a macro model (Ply property), and will make sure that GENOA can precisely analyze the behaviors of the sandwich construction. The properties used for the macro model are shown in Table 4.2. The specifications of thin sandwich material beam and thick sandwich material beam are shown in Fig. 4.1 and Fig. 4.2. The analytical result (Load-Strain) of the SDW_Thin is shown in Fig.4.3 and the analytical result of the SDW_Thick is shown in Fig. 4.4.

Table 4.1 Property values of the aluminum honeycomb 1/8-5052-002 (Showa Aircraft Industry Co. Ltd and JAXA data.)

Category	Name	Item	Core	Unit
Core		1/8-5052-002		
		longitudinal modulus(11)	1.000E+02	MPa
		transverse modulus(22)	1.000E+02	MPa
		transverse modulus(33)	5.000E+03	MPa
		inplane shear modulus(12)	1.000E+01	MPa
		transverse shear modulus(23)	3.600E+02	MPa
		shear modulus(13)	8.100E+02	MPa
		poisson's ratio(12)	0.001	
		poisson's ratio(23)	0.05	
		poisson's ratio(13)	0.49	
		compressive strength(33)	6.865E+00	MPa
		crush strength(33)	3.530E+00	MPa
		shear strength(13)	5.884E+00	MPa
		compressive strength(23)	3.040E+00	MPa

Table 4.2 The Ply property value for analysis.

Category	Name	Item	Ply Property	Unit
laminate		T800HB/3633		
		longitudinal modulus(11)	1.564E+05	MPa
		transverse modulus(22)	9.050E+03	MPa
		transverse modulus(33)	9.050E+03	MPa
		inplane shear modulus(12)	5.328E+03	MPa
		transverse shear modulus(23)	3.053E+03	MPa
		shear modulus(13)	5.328E+03	MPa
		poisson's ratio(12)	0.26	
		poisson's ratio(23)	0.394	
		poisson's ratio(13)	0.26	
		longitudinal tensile strength(11)	2.378E+03	MPa
		longitudinal compressive strength(11)	2.079E+03	MPa
		transverse tensile strength(22)	8.066E+01	MPa
		transverse compressive strength(22)	2.375E+02	MPa
		inplane shear strength(12)	7.736E+01	MPa
		longitudinal flexural modulus(11)	1.564E+05	MPa
		transverse flexural modulus(22)	9.050E+03	MPa
		flexural strength(23)	5.361E+01	MPa
		flexural strength(1F)	2.773E+03	MPa
		flexural strength(2F)	1.505E+02	MPa
	flexural strength(SB)	1.160E+02	MPa	
core		AL 1/8-5052-002		
		longitudinal modulus(11)	1.000E+02	MPa
		transverse modulus(22)	1.000E+02	MPa
		transverse modulus(33)	5.000E+03	MPa
		inplane shear modulus(12)	1.000E+01	MPa
		transverse shear modulus(23)	3.600E+02	MPa
		shear modulus(13)	8.100E+02	MPa
		poisson's ratio(12)	0.001	
		poisson's ratio(23)	0.05	
		poisson's ratio(13)	0.49	
		longitudinal tensile strength(11)	5.884E+00	MPa
		longitudinal compressive strength(11)	5.884E+00	MPa
		transverse tensile strength(22)	3.040E+00	MPa
		transverse compressive strength(22)	3.040E+00	MPa
		inplane shear strength(12)	5.884E+00	MPa
		longitudinal flexural modulus(11)	1.000E+02	MPa
		transverse flexural modulus(22)	1.000E+02	MPa
		flexural strength(23)	6.865E+00	MPa
		flexural strength(1F)	6.865E+00	MPa
		flexural strength(2F)	6.865E+00	MPa
	flexural strength(SB)	6.865E+00	MPa	

Fig.4.1 Specification of thin sandwich beam

Fig.4.2 Specification of thick sandwich beam

Fig.4.3 Four-point flexure of SDW_thin

Fig.4.4 Four-point flexure of SDW_thick

The experimental result (failure mode) of the SDW_Thin means that the central part of the face sheet is broken as shown in the Fig4.5. The analytical result of GENOA shows that when load approaches 5.23 (KN), the upper face sheet starts deterioration caused by compressive load, the damage propagates, and it finally leads to failure of the upper face sheet as shown in the Fig4.6.

In the case of SDW_Thick, since the load was applied until the start of destruction in the experiment, we could not capture the exact load causing complete failure of the sandwich beam. However, visual check after the experiment told that the core started deterioration near the loading points. The analytical result of GENOA shows that the compressive damage of the core caused by compressive load starts when the load is 3.51 (KN), as shown in Fig. 4.7. When the load reaches to 7.06(KN), the damage propagates to the outside of loading points of the core as shown in Fig.4.8.

Fig.4.5 The photograph of the damage mode

Fig.4.6 The damage situation of the SDW_Thin when the load is 5.23(KN)

Fig.4.7 The damage situation of the SDW_Thick when the load is 3.51(KN)

Fig.4.8 The damage situation of the SDW_Thick when the load is 7.06(KN)

5. Discussions

We verified that the compressive properties of the laminate sheet acquired by the experiment of the SDW_Thin is effective in our intended analysis. It is easy to apply pure compressive situation in the experiment of the SDW_Thin, though it is difficult to apply pure compressive situation in the examination of the compressive test of 0° coupon laminate. Moreover, we verified that it is possible to estimate the behaviors of the sandwich beam in the

SDW_Thin not by the use of solid element model but by the use of shell element model.

When we analyzed the compressive test of 45 degree laminate using the SDW_Thin property values presented in Table 2.2, we obtained the result shown in Fig. 5.1. The result shows significant difference of strength between experiment and analysis. In order to eliminate this difference, it is necessary to raise the shear strength of a matrix. However, if the shear strength of a matrix increases, then it will cause significant difference between experiment and analysis for tensile test of 45 degree lamination and for compressive quasi-isotropic laminate is as shown in Fig.5.2. Most commercial simulation codes do not allow the difference of properties in tension and compression. This is a keen requirement. As a trial, we adopted the longitudinal tensile stiffness so that the S-S curve of the tensile test of 0 degree laminate becomes similar to that of simulation, as shown in Fig.5.3, and the compressive stiffness so that the S-S curve of the compressive test of 0 degree laminate becomes similar to that of simulation, as shown in Fig.5.4. The load-strain prediction of the SDW_Thick becomes closer to an experimental result as shown in Fig. 5.5 when upper face and back face sheets are modeled as the compressive and tensile stiffness, respectively. In the case of a simple model, it is possible that users can apply different properties in tension and compression. But in the case of actual model, it is difficult that users set up different properties in tension and compression because of complex stress situation. We expect that this issue is resolved in the future simulation systems.

Fig5.1 The compressive test of 45 degree laminate with the improvement shear strength of matrix

Fig.5.2 The compressive pseudo isotropy laminate with the improvement shear strength of matrix

Fig.5.5 The SDW_Thick with setting up tensile and compressive property

Fig.5.3 The tensile test of 0 degree with the improvement tensile stiffness

Fig.5.4 The compressive test of 0 degree with the improvement compressive stiffness

References

- [1] Yokozeki T., Ogasawara T., Hatta H, and Ishikawa T., "Compressive Strength Evaluation of Unidirectional CFRP Using Sandwich Beam Specimen in Flexure" *Proceedings of Annual Meeting of JSCM, Tokyo, pp.87-88, 2006.*